

Invited talk

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17532501>

COMPUTING WITH WORDS AND PERCEPTIONS

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Computing with words and perceptions is based on fuzzy logic, a way of doing science without mathematics. It is the branch of artificial intelligence that tries to make computers think the way we humans do. Often humans cannot get science right to the point, computing with words and perceptions offers common-sense solutions.